

Types, Uses and Influence of Social Media Among Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study determined the types, uses and influence of social media usage among senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey design. The population of the study comprised of 13,645 SS students and a sample of 375 was selected through the multistage and simple sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was "Types, purpose and influence of Social Media among Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State". The validation of the instrument was done through the face and content validity while the reliability was determined using the test re-test method which yielded 0.93 coefficient index. Simple percentage and Mean were used for data analysis. The finding indicated that Facebook, 2go, Whatsapp, Instagram, and You Tube were common social media sites used by the students. The study's finding also showed that students use the social media for the purpose of finding friends online, for leisure and socialization, for watching movies, for political matters, and for uploading photos and online profiles. The findings further revealed poor academic performance, indiscipline and immoral behaviour of the students as influences of social media usage. It was recommended that teachers and school managers should integrate usage of social media sites into the school programmes for enhancing students' social and academic behaviours. Students' orientation programme on social media usage was also suggested, among others.

Key words: *Types, Uses, Influence, Social Media and Senior Secondary School Students*

Introduction

Social media has rapidly changed the process of communication globally in the social world. Students at all levels of education have been very much interested in utilizing various forms of social networking sites for communication. The social media may be seen as

technologically designed packages for the purpose of sharing information and communication. Social media sites are used to connect friends, photos, videos and games as well as sharing of documents for academic and social purposes. As a platform, the social media enables people and especially students to communicate with ease on academic and social issues through texts, images, audios, maps, and videos. According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), social media is an internet-based application that allow the creation and exchange of content amongst the users. The term “social media” is defined by Raymond and Afua (2016), as the application that allows users to converse and interact with each other; to create, edit and share new forms of textual, visual and audio content; and to categorize, label and recommend existing forms of content. Social media therefore is a wide collection of internet based and mobile services that connect people together to communicate, participate, collaborate, discuss and exchange ideas and information on an online window.

There are many forms of social media which allow users or students specifically to interact with other media users of their choice (Gina, 2018). Prominent among these include Facebook, Twitter, Badoo, Mozat, 2go, Whatsapp, Instagram, Iskimi, My Life, You Tube, Yahoo, BBM, and many others. Thus, Lynn, Healy, Kilroy, Hunt, Werff, Venkatagiri and Morrison (2015) considered social media as one of the game-changers in the realm of learning and instruction. Ovute and Ovute (2015) also discussed the implications of social media in providing quality education for different categories of learners in schools, colleges and universities. McLoughlin and Lee (2010) stated that using the social media in the educational process could help educators to apply the inquiry-based approach and encourage the collaboration between the teacher and the students, thereby encouraging positive engagement for better academic outcomes. Social media also encourage independent self-directed learning as well as active participation during the teaching-learning process by teachers and the students (Dumpit & Fernandez, 2017). Students therefore use the various platforms of the social media to achieve their educational needs and goals.

Based on the foregoing, it suffices to state that students at all levels use the social media in different ways which have influence on their academic performance and social behaviours. The influence could be positive or negative. The positive influence of social media sites works with the individual student when he/she uses it to share and receive documents and relevant academic materials for study purposes and pro-social behaviour while it could be negative if a student uses it to share and receive unethical images, videos and negative documentary such as pornographies (Raymond & Afua, 2016). Hence, social media usage by students improves their academic achievements (Ovute & Ovute, 2015). On the other hand, social media sites open up new ways for collaboration and discussion on social and academic matters through offering of a great deal of content posting, coping, sharing and search ability, using the online search tools. The negative influence of the social media, on the other hand, may include laziness, low academic performance due to social media addiction, poor writing skills, imitation and coping of immoral behaviour, delinquency, rioting and vandalism, and other forms of school indiscipline (Morgan, Grahah & Hodges, 2012).

Against this backdrop, students at all levels use the social media sites anyway anyhow which has consequences on their educational and social development (Gurcan, 2015). It is as a result of this phenomenon, this study seeks to assess the types, usage and influence of social media among senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State in order to provide guidance in the formulation of policies, programmes and learning strategies toward achieving the desired educational goals in the zone particularly and the state at large. The use of social media by students has positive and negative influence on their social, academic and personality profiles (e.g., it may affect their engagement in academic exercises and social activities such as interest, skill development, knowledge base and intellectual abilities). This justifies why students should be regulated and monitored on social media usage in terms of when, where, how, with whom and for what purposes they engage in utilizing the social media sites. Also, addiction to social media by students could lead to the tendency of loneliness, laziness and increased feelings of insensitivity to the social world. Hence, there is need to fashion out research findings with the view of assessing the types, uses and influence of social media either positively or negatively on social and academic behaviours of secondary schools students which this study is concerned to achieve in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the following:

1. Types of social media sites commonly used among senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State.
2. Purpose of using social media among senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State.
3. Influence of social media usage on the social and academic behaviours of senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, the following questions were asked:

1. What are the types of social media sites commonly used among senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State?
2. What do senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State use social media for?
3. What is the influence of social media usage on the social and academic behaviours of senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State?

Method

Descriptive survey research design was used in this study. This design was considered appropriate because it permits the researchers to study a sample size with the view of generalizing the study's findings on the entire target population.

The population of this study comprised of all senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State. Minna Educational Zone comprised of Chanchaga, Bosso,

Paikoro, Shiroro, and Rafi Local Government Areas. There are 13,645 senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State (Planning, Research and Statistics Department (PRS) of the Niger State Ministry of Education, Minna (2018).

The sample size for this study is 375 senior secondary II students. This sample size was determined using the Research Advisors Sample Size Table (2006). A multistage sampling technique was used by grouping the Minna Educational Zone into three (3) sub-zones; comprising of Shiroro Zone (covering Shiroro, Rafi and Munya Local Governments Areas), Minna Zone (this consists of Chanchaga and Bosso Local Governments Areas), and Paikoro Zone (covering Paiko and Kafinkoro Areas). One Local Government Area was selected from each sub-zone through the simple random sampling (giving a total of three Local Government Areas). Five (5) schools were chosen randomly from each Local Government Area (making a total of 15 schools). In each school, 25 participants were randomly selected for the study; making a total of 375 students.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire titled "Types, Usage and Influence of Social Media on Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State". The instrument comprised of section A which centered on the demographic data of the participants and section B which was made up of 33 item statements that answer the research questions. The items were structured on a four-point modified Likert's scale namely; Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed; and were scored as 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The researchers used 2.5 as the mean point for taking decision on whether to agree and disagree) for a particular item, which served as an indicator for measuring the research questions. An item with a mean point of 2.5 and above was taken to be that the respondent agreed while an item with a mean point less than 2.5 was taken to imply that the respondent disagreed.

The data collection instrument was given to two lecturers in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Department of the Federal University of Technology, Minna and one lecturer of Educational Psychology from the Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai to determine the face and content validity of the items. Based on their scrutiny and suggestions some questions were modified, some dropped and others added in order to make the instrument valid.

A test retest method to ascertain the reliability of the instrument was used on a pilot study of 30 students from two (2) senior secondary schools in Wushishi Local Government Area which is outside the sampled areas of the study. The instrument was administered on the students at an interval of two weeks and the results were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) which was tested at 0.05 levels of significance. A coefficient value of 0.93 was obtained which implies that the instrument was highly reliable.

The procedure for data collection was undertaken by the researchers for a period of two days. Copies of the instrument were distributed to the research participants through the group method and the filled questionnaires were collected on the spot. The data collected were analysed using the descriptive statistics. Specifically, simple percentage and mean were used to answer the research questions.

Results

Table 1.

Types of Social Media Sites used by Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone

S/N	Types of social media applications used	Mean	Decision
1	Facebook	3.7	Agreed
2	Twitter	2.1	Disagreed
3	Badoo	2.1	Disagreed
4	Mozat	1.6	Disagreed
6	2go	3.4	Agreed
7	Whatsapp	3.2	Agreed
8	Istagram	3.00	Agreed
9	Iskimi	3.1	Agreed
10	My Life	1.3	Disagreed
11	You Tube	2.7	Agreed
12	Yahoo	1.8	Disagreed
13	BBM	2.7	Agreed

Table1 identified types of social media applications commonly used by the senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State. Majority of the participants with mean of items ranging from 3.7 - 2.8 indicated that they use the following social media tools greatly: Facebook (3.7),2go (3.4), Whatsapp (3.2), Iskimi (3.1), Istagram (3.0), You Tube (2.7) and BBM (2.7).However, Twitter (2.1), Badoo (2.1), Yahoo (1.8), Mozat (1.6), and My Life (1.3) were types of social media applications that are not often used by the students.

Table 2.

Purpose of Using Social Media by Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone

S/N	Purpose of using the social media	Mean	Decision
1	I have use the social media applications for communicating and interacting with friends	3.2	Agreed
2	I have use the social media applications for online learning	2.1	Disagreed
3	I have use the social media applications for finding friends online	3.5	Agreed

4	I have used use the social media sites for leisure and personal socialization	3.5	Agreed
5	I have use the social media sites for academic purposes (e.g., group discussion and getting study partners online)	2.2	Disagreed
6	I have use the social media applications for watching movies	3.7	Agreed
7	I have use the social media applications for connecting and interacting with business partners	2.1	Disagreed
8	I have use the social media applications for communicating and mobilizing religious issues in the country	1.3	Disagreed
9	I have use the social media applications for private messaging, uploading photos and online profiles	3.8	Agreed
10	I have use the social media applications for communicating and mobilizing political matters in the country	3.6	Agreed

Table 2 showed that the respondents agreed to all the items as the purpose of using social media except items 5, 2, 7, and 8. This finding indicated that students used social media applications for the purpose of private messaging, uploading photos and online profiles (3.8), for watching movies (3.7), for mobilizing political matters (3.6), for finding friends online (3.5), for leisure and personal socialization (3.5) and for communicating and interacting with friends (3.2).

Table 3.

Influence of Social Media usage on the Social and Academic Behaviours of Senior Secondary School Students in Minna Educational Zone

S/N	Influence of Social Media Usage	Mean	Decision
1	Social media influences ones academic performance when the usage is not monitored	3.4	Agreed
2	Social media leads to internet addiction	2.8	Agreed
3	Social media causes laziness among students	3.3	Agreed
4	Social media leads to criminal acts (e.g., for instance, kidnapping, fraud, murder)	3.6	Agreed
5	Social media causes acts of indiscipline and immoral behaviour	3.9	Agreed
6	Social media affects students' writing skills	3.7	Agreed
7	Social media leads to delinquency among students	3.4	Agreed
8	Social media causes waste of time on chatting instead of reading or studying	3.7	Agreed
9	Social media affects one's concentration in a class	3.6	Agreed
10	Social media encourages negative peer group influence among students in school	3.5	Agreed

Table 3 determined the influence of social media usage on social and academic behaviours of senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone, Niger State. The findings indicated that all the items of the instrument have means above 2.5. This implies that social media usage has influence on social and academic behaviours of the senior secondary students in Minna Educational Zone.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings revealed that Facebook, 2go, Whatsapp, Iskimi, Instagram, You Tube and BBM were the types of social media applications commonly used by senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State. This finding corroborated the study of Okereke and Lucky (2014), which found that the social media often used by students are Facebook, Whatsapp and 2go/Skype. Similarly, the study of Raymond and Afua (2016) indicated Facebook, WeChat, WhatsApp and YouTube as social media types commonly used by the students of Higher Education. Also, Gurcan (2015) stated that social media have dominated students' life with Facebook, WeChat, WhatsApp, and LinkedIn used mostly by them. Eke-Okpala and Omekwu (2014), conducted a research and reported that the response scores on the extent of the usage of social networking sites by undergraduate students of the University of Nigeria Nsukka were more in favour of Facebook, 2go, Yahoo, Whatsapp, Googl+, Youtube, Skype and Blackberry messenger.

The findings of this study also showed that students used social media for the purpose of private messaging, uploading photos and online profiles, for watching movies, for mobilizing political matters, for finding friends online, for leisure and personal socialization and for communicating and interacting with friends. Agreeing with this finding, Okereke and Luck (2014), stated that students used social media for reaching out to close/distance friends and for sourcing information about life. Besides, Raymond and Afua (2016) study which stressed that the social media has been a medium of receiving and sending information in the school life of students agreed with the findings of this study. Related findings with this study by Ovute and Ovute (2015) found that social media allow people to identify with other users, with whom they have a connection, and send and receive messages either privately or publicly. Gurcan (2015) in line with findings of this study posited that the possible threats associated with social media sites are too great, because students engage in a private relationship outside the classroom circles which eventually lead to inappropriate behaviours. Eke-Okpala and Omekwu (2015) concluded that social media users often include their interest and they locate members with similar interests by searching for key words and key phrases for the purpose of reuniting with old friends. Dumpit and Fernandez (2017), further stressed the purpose of using the social media sites among students include personal socialization and political mobilization, watching movies, finding friends online and engagement in games. In line with the context of the problem of this study therefore, it has been established that students use the social media for personal, social and political purposes. The study's findings further indicated that social media usage has influence on social and academic behaviours of the senior secondary students in Minna Educational Zone. Students waste time in watching pornography materials and searching for online friends at the detriments

of their academic progress and morality (Eke-Okpala & Omekwu, 2015). In conformity with this result, a study conducted by Okereke and Lucky (2014), revealed that social media cause low performance among Nigeria students. Michikyan, Subrahmanyam and Dennis (2015), carried out a research and concluded that students with low GPAs are more active on Facebook. Also, a research conducted by Gina (2018) discovered that the majority of the participants use the social media in academic related issues and other purposes such as games, social and political matters. Furthermore, the study of Lau (2017) and Janssen and Brumby (2010), posited that social media is a predictor of a poor academic performance and delinquent acts among students.

Based on the findings above, it has been justified that the social media usage has the tendency of affecting students' academic exercise, and may lead to internet addiction, influence of bad friends and peers, as well as indiscipline and immoral behaviours among students.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it could be concluded that senior secondary school students in Minna Educational Zone of Niger State commonly used Facebook, 2go, Whatsapp, Iskimi, Instagram, You Tube and BBM. The purposes for using the social media among the students include private messaging, uploading photos and online profiles, watching movies, political mobilization and interaction with friends, leisure and personal socialization. The influence of social media usage on the students include poor academic performance and writing skills, indiscipline, immoral behaviours and encourages influence of bad friends and peers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers, school managers and parents should integrate, deploy and utilize Facebook, 2go, Whatsapp, Iskimi, Instagram, You Tube and BBM in teaching and learning process to promote positive usage of the platforms among students in order to enhance their social and academic behaviours.
2. Schools should prioritize students' orientation programmes. This will assist greatly to provide information and guidance on usage of social media sites.
3. Parents and school management should monitor students' usage of internet and other Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities both at homes and schools to regulate their excesses and abuses in using the social media sites. This could be achieved by designing software to enable school managers control the usage of social media among secondary school students to navigate its negative impact as well as imposing school disciplinary measures by a way of meting out sanctions/punishments on violators accordingly.

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